
EDUCATION CREATION TRAINING MULTIMEDIA - MEANS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7872540>

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Abstract.

The article proposes a model of an educational multimedia tool, and a technology for its creation, independent of the choice of a computer system. Implementation given technology will allow bachelors on direction training "Pedagogical education" form professional competencies in areas creation training multimedia funds.

Keywords.

Multimedia tool, interactivity, interface, informational technology, software facilities, electronic educational materials, informational competence.

Introduction.

AT connections with transition humanity in new post-industrial era of its existence, over the next few decades, education will obviously change more than in all three hundred odd years, past with moment occurrence schools contemporary type. Society, in which education becomes authentic capital and the main resource, makes new demands on educational institutions in terms of their educational activities and responsibility for it. The ways in which teaching material is assimilated and presented by teachers are undergoing significant changes, partly the result of a new understanding of the learning process, and partly the result of the emergence, implementation and use of new information technologies. [1]

Main Part. Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan approved projects and programs in the field of education aimed at the development of educational systems in conditions informatization society. Let's list main from them [2]:

□ target program development education on the 2005 - 2010 years. aim programs is an "security conditions to meet the needs of citizens, society and the labor market in quality education through creation new institutional regulatory mechanisms in the field of education, updating the structure and content education, development fundamentality and practical orientation of educational programs, the formation of a system of continuous education". One same from results implementation of this program is to increase the proportion of students

receiving education using information technology, 1.5 times compared to with 2005 year[3].

□National project "Education " in which entered on the- governing body "Introduction contemporary educational technologies", whose main activities are the development and placement in the public domain on the Internet information educational resources, connecting schools to the Internet, purchasing and supplying educational institutions of computer equipment; and so- same equipment schools educational and visual allowances and equipment [4].

Model "Education 2025". AT developed model "Education - 2025" laid down four fundamental areas of development: the availability of quality education for any resident of the country and its continuity, the orientation of the education system towards the innovative development of the economy, its openness to society, which includes taking into account the interests of consumers of educational services, and the possibility of an external, public assessment of the level of institutions and their educational programs [5].

The implementation of these projects is impossible without the training of teachers, able to quickly adapt to rapidly changing conditions of professional activity, new information technologies and communication systems that infiltrated and become integral component any contemporary professions. [6]

In the State standards of the second generation of higher professional education on directions training bachelors: 540100 – natural science education; 540200 – physical mathematics education, 540300 - philological education; 540400 - socio-economic education; 540500 - technological education; 540600 - pedagogy; 540700 - artistic education, approved on January 31, 2005, in paragraph 7.1. "Requirements to professional preparedness bachelor's degree, says about the ability of graduates to acquire new knowledge using modern informational educational technologies.

In this regard, the State standard for the preparation of bachelors the discipline "Information and communication technologies" is included in education".

In the standards of the third generation of higher professional education in the direction of training "Pedagogical education", already professional tasks of the bachelor are clearly formulated, one of which is: the use of educational environment opportunities to ensure the quality of education, including with the use of information technologies. In addition, the following general cultural (OK) competencies, related with implementation information technologies in professional activity bachelor's degree:

1. Owns the basic methods, ways and means of obtaining, storing, processing information, has computer skills as means information management (OK-8);

2. Able to work with information in global computer networks (OK-9). [7]

Let's pay attention to the new requirements for the teacher, which in the fall 2009 were recorded in the Unified Qualification Handbook (EKS), which determines the qualification characteristics of position education workers (—Appendix to the Order of the Ministry of Education Republic of Uzbekistan from 08/14/2009 No. 593I). The Order states that the requirements imposed by the CEN on educators are aimed at increasing the effectiveness of their labor, labor activity, business initiative and competence. At this under competence understood quality action worker, providing an adequate and effective solution professionally significant subject tasks, wearing problem character. To main components of the competence of educators include: professional, communicative, innovative, legal, informational. [8]

Informational competence - quality action employee, providing effective search, structuring of information, its adaptation to the peculiarities of the pedagogical process and didactic requirements, the formulation of the educational problem by various information and communication ways, qualified work with various information resources, professional tools, ready-made software and methodological complexes that allow you to design a solution to pedagogical problems and practical tasks, the use of automated workstations of the teacher in the educational process; regular independent cognitive activity, readiness to administered remote educational activities, the use of computer and multimedia technologies, digital educational resources in the educational process, conducting school documentation on the electronic carriers. [9]

To solve professional problems of bachelors in the field of information technologies and formation given higher competencies, we offer a solution to a complex problem, namely, the creation educational multimedia tool. Implementation of the solution of the specified problem bachelor's degree, will allow him to master the following types of professional activities:

1. Knowledge of methods of obtaining, storing, processing information; computer technology that can be used in lessons; fundamentals of methods and techniques for the application of modern technical funds in educational process; [10]

2. Ability to use computer technology in visual demonstrations on a specific topic; select ready-made information educational resources and methods for their use on lesson; use the resources of the global Internet; analyze the quality of computer models and teaching aids from the point of view of scientific credibility and compliance requirements to audiovisual materials; analyze their own activities on the use of information technologies in order to increase its effectiveness; [11]

3. possessions technical means and informational technologies learning. [12]

These activities will be mastered in stages in the process of creating a multimedia educational tool. Destination.

In addition, the solution of a complex problem using multimedia technologies will solve a number of problems associated with the development of new software and hardware that are being introduced into the educational process. [13]

On the one hand, to acquaint with the existing variety of ready-made educational multimedia tools. Currently in educational institutions wide are used educational multimedia programs of the following types: encyclopedic publications, reference books, educational multimedia programs; educational publications; artistic works with elements learning; guidebooks; directories. [14]

On the other hand, to teach how to create their own educational multimedia tools, using software and hardware that has various functionality.

To do this, the author developed a technology for creating educational multimedia means independent of the computer system. The technology includes three stages: building a basic model of educational multimedia facilities, selection content component educational multimedia facilities, implementation educational multimedia means. [15]

Consider each of the stages of the technology for creating educational multimedia facilities. one. Building basic models educational multimedia Wednesdaysstva. The stage determines before Total, meaningful line multimedia learning tools and involves the implementation of the methodology teaching the content of the subject area using the appropriate learning tool. The main activity of the bachelor at this stage will consist in the following:

1. Formulate appointment educational multimedia tools.

2. To carry out a rationale for the relevance of the development, for this it is necessary: 1.1. Highlight goals applications product;

1.2. Determine the pedagogical tasks that will be solved with using developed educational multimedia tools;

1.3. Analyze similar educational multimedia facilities, if such exist.

3. Highlight significant with points vision goals modeling properties of the educational multimedia tool, which should then be reflected in models.

4. Determine the types of educational material that will be used submitted content multimediatoools learning (explanatory, control and measuring, reference and etc.).

5. Consider ways of presenting educational material (text descriptions, illustrations, sound escort, animations).

6. Describe how components can be interconnected (hyperlinks, managers buttons, pop-up hints and other).

7. Choose form models, For example, scheme, table, algorithm and So Further.

8. Present the educational media model in the selectedform. [16]

The developed model will meet the following requirements: it can be implemented on any platform, in the environment of any a software tool designed to create such tools, andwithin any subject area (biology, geography, Russian language and literature etc.). With taking into account this was base model built educational multimedia tools. [17]

Building educational multimedia tools. Selection content component educational multimedia facilities.

At the second stage, the content of the typical components of the content and technological modules of the educational multimedia is selected. facilities. [18]

AT process creation meaningful module teacher necessarydevelop or select existing educational objects (text, graphics, sound, video), process them using information technology, compose and unite in reference encyclopedic block, block electronic abstract and control test materials. [19]

The reference and encyclopedic block may contain biographical data and data on the main scientific achievements of scientists in con- specific subject areas; information reflective results new scientific research and development prospects in this area, basic concepts and definitions on the topic, section, subject and be presented in form dictionary, glossary, index, thesaurus, directory.

The block of the electronic abstract is a summary of the multimedia tool, structured by educational topics and consists of two sections: explanatory and illustrative and problem section tasks. The explanatory and illustrative section organizes the reproductive level of educational and cognitive activity. This block can be presented as a set of structured lectures. Chapter problematic tasks

organizes productive level educational cognitive activity. It includes in myself totality problematic tasks, structured on topics lectures. [20]

problematic task is a form of organization of educational material that requires special conditions for its execution: time, additional information, skills, etc. Examples of a problematic task can be tasks to establish causal connections, definition continuity between facts, determining the degree of progressiveness of a phenomenon, situational tasks and t. d. [21]

A block of control and test materials can be presented in the form of control works, final questions, individual tasks, tests of various forms and refer to one of the types of pedagogical control: input, current and final. [22]

Software simulators are programs for developing skills and abilities of a certain activity, as well as developing related activities. abilities [3]. This component of the content block of the educational multimedia tool is taken out of the scope of education at the university, since requires additional deep knowledge in the field of programming and development program funds. [23]

In the process of creating educational multimedia tools, the above components can be implemented at a higher level, indifference from conventional educational materials, due to the use of sound escort, visualization, animation, method modeling problematic tasks, feedback between the educational material and the student. [24]

AT framework creation technological module multimedia toolsthe teacher thinks through the graphical interface of the future educational multimedia facilities.

At this necessary consider main properties interface training multimedia funds: uniformity, friendliness, structuredness dialogue, ability find and handle mistakes users. Development interface educational multimedia tools includesdecision next major tasks: [25]

□definition composition and attributes windows; □developmentschemes representationinformation;

□determination of means providing navigation through educational material;
□choice color gamma.

Execute the content selection step component multimedia -facilities allows go to next. Implementation educational multimedia means. [26]

The implementation stage involves: filling the content of the subject area with the elements of the model of a multimedia tool for educational purposes, establishing navigational connections between elements and experimental

operation of multimedia tools in the educational process. The result of this stage is a completed functional and content plans educational multimedia tool. Creation work educational multimedia tools ongoing with using multiple software and hardware. As a software software, it is recommended to use authoring systems. Using the authoring system is, in fact, an accelerated form of programming, where there is no need to delve into the intricacies of the language or the details. API (Application Programming Interface - application interface programs) [4]. It takes much less time to develop a multimedia tool in the author's system than when using pure programming tools. Moreover, to create multimedia components (graphics, text, video, sound) selection of copyrights system is not affected. Reduction of time in the preparation of the final product is achieved through the use of ready-made multimedia templates. facilities learning. [27]

Conclusions

The considered technology is a generalized algorithm for the development of an educational multimedia tool. The proposed algorithm does not depend on the subject area or on the chosen author's system that will be used to create educational multimedia means.

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